

Awareness and Acceptance of Labour Analgesia by Prospective Beneficiaries at the Benue State University Teaching Hospital (Bsuth), Makurdi, Benue State, Nigeria.

¹Efu ME, ²Ojabo AO, ²Hembah-Hilekaan SK, ²Eka PO, ³Anenga UM

¹ Department of Anaesthesia and Intensive Care, Benue State University Teaching Hospital, Makurdi, Benue State, Nigeria.

² Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, College of Health Sciences, Benue State University, Makurdi, Benue State, Nigeria. ³ Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Benue State University Teaching Hospital, Makurdi, Benue State, Nigeria.

*Correspondence: Dr Michael Enokela Efu, Department of **Article information**

Anaesthesia and Intensive Care, Benue State University Teaching Hospital, Makurdi, Benue State, Nigeria Date Submitted 27/10/2023

Date Accepted 14/11/2023 E-mail: enokelaefu@gmail.com Phone: +2348036259075

Date Published: 29/11/2023

ABSTRACT

Background: The pain of childbirth is perhaps the most severe pain most women will experience in their lifetime. While pain of the first stage of labour is triggered by stretching of the mechanoreceptors, pain of the second stage of labour is caused by distension of pelvic structures and perineum due to the descent of the presenting part. Historically, there were several descriptions of various methods that were used to relieve the sufferings of the labouring women. Opposition to labour analgesia came from both the church and the medical community. An extremely important step in the development of labour analgesia was the use of nitrous oxide in 1880. At the moment, lumbar epidural block is considered as the gold standard of intrapartum analgesia. **Objective:** This study was conducted to ascertain the level of awareness and the acceptance of labour analgesia amongst pregnant women attending the ante natal clinic at the Benue State University Teaching Hospital. Findings from the study would serve as a guide to establishing labour analgesia services in the institution. **Methodology:** This was a cross sectional study conducted amongst pregnant women who attended the ante natal clinic of the Benue State University teaching Hospital Makurdi, by the use of questionnaire. The sample size was calculated using the Kish Leslie formula for cross sectional studies, $n = Z^2Pq/d^2$. Consultants, resident doctors, nurses and sometimes, medical students administered the questionnaires. The questionnaire contained demographics as well as other pertinent items. Data collected were analyzed using SPSS version 25 using simple statistics. **Results:** A total of 275 respondents were enrolled into the study. The age bracket between 25 to 29 years recorded the highest number of respondents with an average age of 29.84 ± 4.52 years. A majority of those sampled, 238, (98.3%) were married. Majority of the sample population, 196, (71.3%) were of Tiv ethnic group. A majority, 263 (95.6%), were of the Christian faith. Also, majority of the sample population, 232 (84.4%), had tertiary education. One hundred and thirty-nine, (50.5%) of respondents were gainfully employed. The average gestational age was 29.41 ± 7.59 weeks. One hundred and fifty-six (56.0%), had no awareness at all, while 7 (2.5%) were very much aware. Fifty (41.3%) got information through their attending physicians while 30 (26.4%) got through their friends. On whether respondents would accept labour analgesia if offered, 213 (77.5%) answered in the affirmative. The most reason

offered for accepting labour analgesia, 143 (67.1%), is that it would make them enjoy pain-free labour. The major

How to cite this article

Efu ME*, Ojabo AO, Hembah-Hilekaan SK, Eka PO, Anenga UM. Awareness and Acceptance of Labour Analgesia by Prospective Beneficiaries at the Benue State University Teaching Hospital (BSUTH), Makurdi, Benue State, Nigeria. *J Biomed Res Clin Pract*: 2023;6(1-2):1-8. DOI: <http://www.jbrcp.org>

Access to the article

Website:

reason offered for rejecting it was that labour is a natural process that should not be interrupted [31 (50.0%)]. All those who professed very much knowledge all said they would accept. Even though, out of those who had no knowledge at all about labour analgesia, 123 would accept and 31 would not accept indicating that 50% of respondents that would reject the offer of labour analgesia were from this group. **Conclusion:** Awareness of labour analgesia is quite low amongst pregnant women attending the ante natal clinic in our institution. On the contrary, the level of acceptance is high. However, we observed that the more awareness they have, the more likely they would accept to be given analgesia during labour. Therefore, it is safe to postulate that there is a high level of acceptability among our clients in BSUTH. The drawbacks remain lack of trained manpower and envisaged high cost of the service that are likely to hamper effective implementation.

Keywords: Awareness; acceptance; labour; analgesia

INTRODUCTION

The pain of childbirth is perhaps the most severe pain most women will experience in their lifetime. Since pain relief in labour has always been encircled with myths and controversies, providing effective and safe analgesia during labour have remained an ongoing challenge.¹

Pain of the first stage of labour is triggered by stretching of the mechanoreceptors. Noxious impulses are carried by sensory nerve from the lower uterine segment (LUS) and cervix, which stimulates the fibers (A δ and C), which accompanying sympathetic nerve endings, travel through paracervical ganglion and hypogastric plexus to the lumbar sympathetic chain which enter the spinal cord at T10, T11, T12 and L1 spinal segments. This pain is visceral in nature, transmitted slowly, poorly confined, primarily in the lower abdomen, but also referred to lumbosacral area, gluteal region and thighs.¹

Pain of the second stage of labour is caused by distension of pelvic structures and perineum due to

descent of the presenting part, ischaemia and frank injury and is carried by somatic afferent nerve fibers that transmit impulses through the pudendal nerve to the spinal cord at S2, S3, and S4 levels. Characteristic of somatic pain, it is sharp and well-localized¹

Painful labour produces several adverse changes in maternal physiology, which have important implications for the foetus too. These include increased respiratory rate, increased cardiac output, decreased uterine contraction, decreased placental perfusion as well as foetal acidaemia and hypoxia, amongst others¹

In the literature on the history of anesthesia, we can find several descriptions of various methods which were used to relieve the sufferings of the labouring women. Medieval manuscripts revealed that methods of treating pain during labour accepted by the church to include use of amulets, semi-precious stones, or magic belts.² Ethyl alcohol was often used by midwives for analgesia, despite the many voices criticizing that it was too frequently used in excessive doses. Often, noncontrolled supply of alcohol put labouring women in a state of drunkenness, disturbing the physiological parturition.³

A new chapter in the history of the delivery analgesia was opened in 1847 when James Young Simpson from Edinburgh, an obstetrician, in spite of opposition from the ecclesial and medical environments, as well as from the society itself, for the first time, administered inhalational chloroform for labour analgesia⁴

Opposition to labour analgesia came from the church who believed that the pain experienced by a woman during labour is a consequence of the curse of Eve for her disobedience in paradise and as such, people should not hinder it.⁴ Simpson tried to fight this theory through both his medical activities as well as the publication of texts of a polemic nature⁵ Opposition from the medical environments was often even more pronounced than on the part of the church community. For example, Charles Meigs (1792-1869) from the USA was a passionate antagonist of any use of anesthesia during labour because he thought that childbirth is a natural process that does not require any medical intervention⁴

As the acceptance for the use of inhaled analgesics during labour increased, other methods were introduced leading to an Austrian physician Richard von Steinbuechel (1865-1952) for the first time using morphine and scopolamine for analgesia in a woman in labour in 1902. Carl Gauss from Freiburg (1875-1957), who studied this technique of anesthesia later called it "twilight sleep".⁶

An extremely important step in the development of labour analgesia was the use of nitrous oxide in 1880 by a Russian doctor Stanislav Kliclowicza from

St.Petersburg⁷ The proportions of 50% of nitrous oxide and 50% of oxygen determined by Michael Tunstall in 1961, turned out to be safe for both the woman and her child, and placing the ready mixture into one container significantly increased the mobility of labouring women using this form of analgesia⁸ This heralded the use of entonox in obstetric analgesia.

One of the most significant steps in the development of intrapartum relief of pain was epidural analgesia. Thirty to thirty-five millilitres of a 0.5% solution of procaine and adrenaline was used for the first time in 1909 by the German physician Walter Stoeckel (1871-1961)⁹ In his

work, he described in details 141 cases of the use of this method, proving that it is highly effective in eliminating pain, and at the same time devoid of side effects typical of then popular method of "twilight sleep".⁹ Currently, lumbar epidural block is considered as "the gold standard" of intrapartum analgesia. ⁴

Although several methods of labour analgesia have evolved over the years, pain relief in labour is still controversial.¹⁰ In developed countries the issue is focused on the choice of methods and complications, while in developing countries, the issues revolve around awareness, acceptability and availability of labour analgesia¹¹ Apart from fear of child birth women may not be aware of the analgesic options for labour.^{12,13,14} Culture, ethnic group, age and education may have a strong influence on the attitude toward pain relief in labour.¹⁰

This study was conducted to ascertain the level of awareness and also to determine the acceptance of labour analgesia amongst pregnant women attending the ante natal clinic at the Benue State University Teaching Hospital. Findings from the study would serve as a guide to establishing labour analgesia services in the institution.

METHODOLOGY

This was a cross sectional study that was conducted amongst pregnant women who attended the ante natal clinic at the Benue State University Teaching Hospital Makurdi, Benue State, Nigeria by the use of questionnaire, between January and April 2022. Only pregnant women that gave their consents were recruited into the study.

The sample size was calculated using the Kish Leslie formula for cross sectional studies¹⁵.

$n = Z^2 Pq/d^2$. Where n is the desired sample size and Z is the standard normal deviate usually set at 1.96, which corresponds to the 95% confidence interval. P is the proportion of pregnant women aware of labour analgesia, which is 21% from a previous study¹⁶. q is the complementary proportion equivalent to one (1) minus P , while d is the degree of accuracy desired (absolute precision), which is 5.0% (0.05).

Thus: $n = 3.842 \times 0.21(1 - 0.21) / 0.0025 = 254.96$

To compensate for non-response (Attrition factor)¹⁵

$N = n / 1 - f$

Where: $f =$ assumed non-response set at 5 %.

$N = 254.96 / 1 - 0.05 = 254.96 / 0.95$

$N = 268.37$

Therefore, the sample size was 268. Since 268 subjects were the minimum required, a total of 275 were recruited for the study.

Consultants, resident doctors, nurses and sometimes, medical students, who had been previously trained, administered the questionnaires. While literate respondents were guided to fill the questionnaires, the not so literate were assisted with the filling by those administering them. Completed questionnaires were

collected and submitted to members of the study team.

The questionnaire contained demographics. Other items contained in the questionnaire include, parity of respondents, previous deliveries and the routes of deliveries, gestational age at presentation as well as the highest educational qualification. Respondents were also asked how much knowledge of labour analgesia they had and how they got the knowledge. Besides, they were asked if they had experienced labour analgesia and to indicate how the experience was. Finally, they were asked to indicate if they would accept labour analgesia and to choose the appropriate reason for accepting or rejecting it, if offered.

Data collected were analyzed with Statistical Package for the Social (and Health) Sciences (SPSS) version 25 using simple statistics.

RESULTS

A total of 275 respondents were enrolled into the study. The age bracket between 25 to 29 years recorded the highest number of respondents with 106 making up 38.5%. The next highest age bracket is that between 30 to 34 years which recorded 101 respondents which is 36.7%. The least figure of 2 (0.7%) was observed with the age bracket between 45 to 49 years (Fig. 1). The average age of respondents was 29.84 ± 4.52 years

Figure 1. Histogram showing age of participants

An overwhelming majority of the respondents, 238, accounting for 98.3% were married (Tab.1). A vast majority of the study population, 196, were of Tiv extraction making up 71.3%. This was followed by the Idomas and Igedes that recorded 25 (9.1%) and 16 (5.8%) respectively (Tab.1). While 263 (95.6%), were of the Christian faith, 12 (4.4%), professed the Islamic faith (Tab.1). A majority of the sample population, 232 (84.4%), had tertiary education. This was followed by those with secondary education, 33 (12.0%), those without formal education, 6 (2.2%) and those with primary education, 4 (1.5%) respectively (Tab.1). One hundred and thirty-nine, (50.5%) were gainfully employed, while 136 (49.5%) were unemployed (Tab. 1).

Table 1. Other biodata variables

Variable	Frequency (N=275)	Per centage (%)
Marital status		
Married	261	94.9
Single	10	3.6
Divorced	4	1.5
Ethnicity		
Tiv	196	71.3
Idoma	25	9.1
Igede	16	5.8
Fulani	10	3.6
Hausa	8	2.9
Igbo	6	2.2
Igala	4	1.5
Others	10	3.6
Religion		
Christianity	263	95.6
Islam	12	4.4
Educational level		
Tertiary	232	84.4
Secondary	33	12.0
Primary	4	1.5
None	6	2.2
Employment status		
Gainfully employed	139	50.5
Unemployed	136	49.5

Eighty-two respondents had a parity of 2 accounting for 29.8%. This was followed by para 1 with 69 (25.1%), nully para, 55 (20.0%), para 3, 51(18.5%), para 4, 1

(4.4%) and para 5, 6 (2.2%) respectively (Tab. 2). One (2.9%), in their first trimester with an average gestational age of 29.41±7.59 weeks. On delivery first trimester, 81 (29.5%), in their second trimester and 8 experience, 173 (62.9%) had spontaneous vaginal delivery (SVD) while 47 (17.1%) had surgical delivery.

Two hundred and twenty (80%) of the respondents were multiparous whereas 55 (20.0 %) were nulliparous (Tab. 2)

Table 2. Frequency of obstetric characteristics

Variable	Frequency (N=275)	Percentage (%)
Parity		
0	55	20.0
1	69	25.1
2	82	29.8
3	51	18.5
4	12	4.4
5	6	2.2
Gestational Age		
First	8	2.9
Second	81	29.5
Third	186	67.6
Previous Delivery		
Nulliparous	55	20.0
SVD	173	62.9

Variable		Frequency (N=275)	Percentage (%)
Knowledge of labour analgesia			
Very much	Enough	7	2.5
Barely		83	30.2
None		154	56.0
Source of information			
Through my doctor		50	41.3
Through a friend		32	26.4
Through the Midwife/Nurse		24	19.8
Through the internet		15	12.5
Had it in any previous labour?			
Yes	6	2.7	
No	215	97.3	
What was your experience?			
Nice	2	33.3	
Bad	2	33.3	
Can't tell	2	33.3	

On whether respondents would accept labour analgesia if offered, 213 (77.5%) answered in the affirmative while

62 (22.5%) said they would not accept (Tab.4). Out of those that answered in the affirmative, 143 (67.1%) With regard to awareness of labour analgesia, 156 believed that it would make them enjoy pain-free labour. (56.0%) had no awareness at all, while 83 (30.2%) were While 28 (13.1%) believed it would eliminate the fear of barely aware even as 31 (11.5%) indicated to have had labour, 27 (12.7%) believed it would make them less enough awareness and 7 (2.5%) were very much aware agitated and 15 (7.1%) were of the opinion that it would (Tab. 3). Concerning the source of information, 50 make them feel good generally about labour (Tab.4).

(41.3%) got it through their attending physicians, 30 Those who said they would not accept the offer of labour (26.4%) got through their friends while 4 (19.8%) and analgesia gave various reasons such as labour being a 15 (12.5%) got it through their nurses/midwives and the natural process that should not be interrupted, 31 internet respectively (Tab.3). Out of those who knew (50.0%); it could be harmful to the baby, 15 (24.2%); it about labour analgesia, only 6 (2.7%) had experienced could result in cesarean section, 6 (9.6%); it is expensive, 4 (6.5%); their husbands not accepting, 4 (6.5%) as well as making them feel less a woman, 2 (3.1%) (Tab.4). The rest, 215 (97.3%), had not experienced it (Tab.3). Furthermore, 2 (33.3%) each had nice experience, bad experience or could not tell their experiences (Tab.3).

Table 4. Attitude towards labour analgesia

Variable	Frequency (N=275)	Percentage (%)
If offered labour analgesia, will you accept it?		
Yes	213	77.5
No	62	22.5
Reason for those who said YES		
I will enjoy pain -free labour	Frequency (N=213) 143	
It will eliminate my fear of labour pain agitated	28	13.1
It will make me feel good about labour generally	15	7.1
Reason for those who said NO		
Labour pain is natural and must not be interrupted	Frequency (N=62)	
It can harm my baby	15	24.2
it will result in my labour ending in CS	6	9.7
My husband will not accept it	4	6.5
It is expensive	4	6.5
It will make me less a woman	2	3.1

Of all those who professed very much knowledge all said they would accept, with none rejecting the offer (Tab.5). Out of those who said they had enough knowledge, 27 respondents said they would accept and 4 said they would reject (Tab.5). Also, out of the respondents that were barely knowledgeable about labour analgesia, 56 said they would accept and 27 said they would reject (Tab.5). Finally, out of those who had no knowledge at all about labour analgesia, 123 said they would accept and 31 would not accept indicating that 50% of respondents that would reject labour analgesia were from this group.

Table 5. Relationship between knowledge about

	If offered labour analgesia, will you accept it?				
	Yes	No	X ²	P-value	
Knowledge about labour analgesia	Very much	7	0	8.941	0.030*

labour analgesia and possible acceptance

Enough	27	4
Barely	56	27
Not at all	3	12

Benue state is blessed with a good number of tertiary institutions such as universities, polytechnics and colleges of education with ownership ranging from Federal, State, Missions to private individuals. Residents in the state naturally take advantage of these schools to get educated. This is responsible for the high percentage of graduates of tertiary institutions recorded amongst the respondents (84.4%). From the results of

the study conducted by Nabukenya et al, while over 50

DISCUSSION

All the participants were within the female reproductive age with the average age of respondents being 29.84±4.52 years. The dominance of the Tiv ethnic group (71.3%) in the study population is understandable in that not only is Makurdi, where sampling took place, a Tiv town, but also the Tivs are the majority ethnic group in Benue State. The other 2 major tribes, Idoma and Igede came second and third respectively. Benue state is majorly a Christian state and therefore, it is not surprising that an overwhelming majority (95.6%) of % had attained at least secondary

respondents were of the Christian faith.

education, the number with primary level education and below is still significant¹⁷. By comparison, women attending antennal clinic in our institution are better educated.

Both the employed and the unemployed are almost evenly distributed (50.5% and 49.5%). Ordinarily, one would have expected a higher level of employment given the level of education of respondents. However, owing to the down turn of the economy, unemployment remains a national issue.

A vast majority of the study population were either barely aware or not at all aware of the existence of labour

analgesia (86.2%), while barely 13.8% fell into the

category of those who were very much aware or had enough awareness. This poor result is in tandem with very similar results in developing countries. The problem in this situation is compounded by the dearth of trained manpower too, which if available and ready should be in the forefront of the campaign for the awareness. In developed countries, because labour analgesia is easily available and accessible, the issue is focused on the choice of methods and complications, while in developing countries, the issues revolve around awareness, acceptability and availability.¹¹ Naithani et al, in their study, found that only 9.5% of the women were aware of the availability of pain relief during labour and this is similar to the result of our study.¹⁸ Our result is less than what obtains nation-wide in our country which has a record of 27%¹¹ and in Lagos with an impressive figure of 38.9%.¹⁹ Australia has an even more impressive 98% awareness level.¹²

knowledge of labour analgesia in the study undertaken institution. On the contrary, the level of acceptance is by Nabukenya et al, the commonest source of high. However, we observed that the more awareness information was friends and relatives. Few received

A majority of the respondents became aware of labour analgesia through their doctors, mid-wives/nurses and friends (87.5%) leaving just 12.5% who self-educated themselves via the internet. Among those who had information from the previous labour, even fewer still from media and literature.¹⁷ From the result of our study, only a mere 2.7% has had any experience of labour analgesia. This is not unexpected when one observes the huge number of the respondents that had little or no awareness of this interventional modality.

The most reason given by respondents for accepting labour analgesia was that labour analgesia would make them enjoy pain-free labour (67.1%). But 50% of those who would reject labour analgesia believed that labour was a natural process that should not be interrupted. It is important to observe also, that a good percentage (24.2%) were of the belief that labour analgesia could be harmful to their babies. In their study, Ibach et al observed that the discrepancy in the level of awareness and acceptance they were able to unearth could be attributed to the fact that child birth is still viewed as a

countries, which is managed with as little interference as possible. Many women still do not know that pain of labour can be relieved²⁰

Corelating awareness and possible acceptance of labour analgesia, 100% of those who professed very much knowledge all said they would accept, with none rejecting the offer. Out of those who said they had enough knowledge, 87.0% respondents said they would accept and 13% would reject. Also, out of the respondents that were barely knowledgeable about labour analgesia, 67.5% said they would accept and 22.5% said they would reject. Finally, out of those who had no knowledge at all about labour analgesia, even though about 80% of them would accept with 20% indicating they would not accept, the 20% from this group of respondents constitute 50% of the total number of respondents that would reject labour analgesia. A significant relationship has, thus, been established

pregnant women attending the ante natal clinic in our institution. On the contrary, the level of acceptance is by Nabukenya et al, the commonest source of high. However, we observed that the more awareness information was friends and relatives. Few received

between awareness and acceptance of labour analgesia.

CONCLUSION

Awareness of labour analgesia is quite low amongst physiological process in most of the developing they have, the more likely they would accept to be given analgesia during labour. Therefore, it is safe to postulate that there is a high level of acceptability among our clients in BSUTH. However, the drawbacks remain lack of trained manpower and envisaged high cost of the service that are likely to hamper effective implementation. We therefore recommend that efforts should be made to train/employ more staff and to equip the hospital towards the commencement of labour analgesia services.

Conflict of interest: The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

REFERENCES

1. Paul A. Labor epidural analgesia: past, present and future. *Indian J Pain* 2014; 28:71-81.
2. Mander, R. Analgesia and anaesthesia in childbirth: obscurantism and obfuscation. *J Adv Nurs* 1998;28(1):86-93.
3. Melzack R, Wall P. *The Challenge of Pain*. London. Penguim, 1991.
4. Michalczyk Michał, Torbé Dorota, Torbé Andrzej. A brief historical outline of the development of labor analgesia. *J. Ed., Health and Sport*. 2018;8(9):827832.
5. Simpson JY. *Answer to the Religious Objections Advanced against the Employment of Anaesthetic Agents in Midwifery and Surgery* Edinburgh: Sutherland and Knox, 1847.
6. Claye AM. *The Evolution of Obstetric Analgesia: Chapter 2 The coming of twilight sleep*. Oxford Medical Publications, 1939.
7. Marx GF, Katsnelson T. The introduction of nitrous oxide analgesia into obstetrics. *Obstet Gynecol* 1992; 80:715.
8. Tunstall ME. Obstetric Analgesia. The use of a fixed nitrous oxide and oxygen mixture from one cylinder. *Lancet* 1961; 2:964.
9. Okeke CI, Merah NA, Cole SU, Osibogun A. 9. Doughty A. Walter Stoeckel: A pioneer of regional analgesia in obstetrics. *Anaesthesia* 1990; 45:468. among prospective parturients at the Lagos
10. Mugambe JM, Nel M, Hiemstra LA, Steinberg WJ. University Teaching Hospital. *Niger Postgrad Med J* Knowledge and attitude toward pain relief during 2005; 12:258-61. labor of women attending the antenatal clinic of
11. Olayemi O, Aimakhu CO, Udoh ES. Attitudes of 97:461-4 patients to obstetric analgesia at the university college hospital, Ibadan, Nigeria. *J Obstet Gynaecol* 2003; 23:38-40.
12. Henry A, Nand SL. Women's antenatal knowledge and plans regarding intrapartum pain management at the Royal Hospital for women. *Aust N Z J Obstet Gynaecol* 2004; 44:314-7.
13. Lavender T, Walkinshaw SA, Walton I. A prospective study of women's views of factors
14. Leap N. Pain in labor: Toward a midwifery perspective. *Midwifery Dig* 2000; 10:49-53.
15. Araoye MO. Sample Size Determination. In: Araoye MO (Editor). *Research methodology with statistics for health and social sciences*. Nathadex publishers. 2003; 6(1): 115–121.
16. Omotayo R S, Akinsowon O, Omotayo S E. Awareness, attitude and use of labor analgesics by pregnant women at State Specialist Hospital, Akure. *Trop J Obstet Gynaecol* 2019; 36:170-6
17. Mary T. Nabukenya1, Andrew Kintu1, Agnes Wabule1, Mark T Muyingo and Arthur Kwizera1. Knowledge, attitudes and use of labour analgesia among women at a low-income country antenatal clinic. *BMC Anesthesiology* (2015) 15:98. DOI 10.1186/s12871-015-0078-9
18. Naithani U, Bharwal P, Chauhan SS, Kumar D, Gupta S, Kirti. Knowledge, attitude and acceptance of antenatal women toward labor analgesia and caesarean section in a medical college hospital in India. *J Obstet Anaesth Crit Care* 2011; 1:13-20.
19. Ibach F, Dyer RA, Fawcus S, Dyer SJ. Knowledge Cecilia Makiwan Hospital, South Africa. *SA Fam and expectations of labor among primigravid* *Pract* 2007; 49:16-24. women in the public health sector. *S Afr Med J* 2007; 11.

contributing to a positive birth experience.
Midwifery 1999; 15:40-6.

